

A REPORT ON THE GEOLOGICAL FIELD MAPPING OF
SHARE, KWARA STATE
NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Kwara state is located approximately between latitude N8°10' and N9°50', longitude E3°10' and E6°5'. Share is situated in Kwara state Nigeria with its geographical coordinates given as 8°49' 0" North and 4°59' 0" East. This area falls in North-Eastern part of Kwara state, and falls under North-Central Nigeria, which was produced by the Federal Survey of Nigeria in 1964. A four day field mapping exercise was carried out in this terrain with the goal of producing a geological map of the area showing spatial distribution of rock units. The locality is majorly dominated with the basement complex of the area (igneous and metamorphic) and also sedimentary basin (metamorphic and sedimentary).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I want to use this opportunity to thank God for making this session's field trip a reality. I also want to thank my parents for their unique love and support. Also I would love to give my thanks to Dr. Owoyemi, Dr. Jimoh, Dr Adepoju and Mr Issa for their guidance and tutorship they offered me and my colleagues during the field trip.

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DEFINITION OF TERMS

The following are terms and their meanings which were used in this report;

- 1) **M:** Meters
- 2) **MM:** Millimeters
- 3) **N:** North (Latitude)
- 4) **E:** East (Longitude)
- 5) **OUTCROP:** The part of a rock formation that appears at the
Surface of the ground or weathered rock mass.
- 6) **STRIKE:** The line of intersection between a horizontal plane and an inclined
plane.
- 7) **DIP:** The line perpendicular to the strike.
- 8) **LATITUDE:** Imaginary lines drawn on maps running north or south of the equator,
Measured in degrees.
- 9) **LONGITUDE:** These are imaginary lines drawn on maps running east or west of
the Greenwich meridian and measured in degrees.
- 10) **SEDIMENTS:** Material derived from pre-existing rock, from biogenic sources, or
precipitated by chemical processes, and deposited at, or near, the Earth's surface.
- 11) **FORMATION:** An area with rocks of same similar lithologies and/or
characteristics.
- 12) **LAMINATION:** Very fine stratification, composed of discrete layers.
- 13) **LAMINAE:** The finest sedimentary layer, less than 1cm in thickness.

- 14) **EPIFAUNA:** These are organisms that live outside the rock.
- 15) **INFAUNA:** These are organisms that live inside the rock.
- 16) **BASEMENT COMPLEX:** The assemblage of both metamorphic & igneous rock underlying stratified rocks in a particular region.
- 17) **SEDIMENTARY BASIN:** A subsiding area of the Earth's crust which permits the net accumulation of sediment.
- 18) **FOLIATION:** A continuous, sub-planar rock fabric formed by the preferred orientation of minerals with a generally platy or tabular habit.
- 19) **LATERITE:** Weathering product of rock, composed mainly of hydrated iron and aluminium oxides and hydroxides, and clay minerals, but also containing some silica.
- 20) **DESICCATION:** Long-term loss of water associated with regional climatic change.
- 21) **APHANITIC:** The descriptive term for small crystals.
- 22) **PHANERITIC:** The descriptive term for larger crystals.
- 23) **LIGNMENT:** This has to do with minerals being aligned in the direction of the minerals.
- 24) **MIGMATITE:** A coarse-grained, heterogeneous mixed rock consisting of: (a) a high-grade metamorphic component with a gneissose texture (see metamorphic grade); and (b) an igneous component with a granite mineralogy and a foliated or un-foliated texture (see foliation). Migmatites are found in high-grade metamorphic terrains where a sequence from high-grade metamorphic rocks through migmatites to granite bodies is often seen in the field.

25) **Lava:** Molten rock, normally a silicate, erupted by a volcano. It may be vesicular, glassy, or porphyritic in texture, and varies between acidic and basic in composition.

26) **RECRYSTALLIZATION:** 1. the growth of new mineral grains from pre-existing mineral grains by the solid-state diffusion of ions in response to a change in temperature, pressure, or composition of the rock system. 2. The changing of crystal fabric or crystal size without an accompanying change in mineral chemistry.

27) **EXFOLIATION:** Weakening and separation of the surface layers of rock as a result of chemical or (possibly) thermal weathering, or of pressure release due to erosion. The decomposition of biotite and hydration of feldspar in granite causes swelling that may lead to failure. Expansion and rock fracturing may also result from temperature change (although this is questioned by many geologists), and sheet failure may result from the release of internal stress in massive rocks when an overburden is removed.

28) **HYDROTHERMAL ACTIVITY:** Any process associated with igneous activity involving the action of very hot waters. The waters involved can be derived directly from an igneous intrusion (i.e. juvenile water) as a residual fluid formed during the late stages of crystallization of the body, or can be external groundwater heated during crystallization of the intrusion. The hydrothermal fluids can react with and alter the rocks through which they pass, or can deposit minerals from solution. Hydrothermal reactions include serpentinization, chloritization, saussuritization, uralitization, and propylitization; whilst hydrothermal vein and replacement mineral deposits include Cu, Pb, and Zn sulphides. Hydrothermal activity should not be confused with geothermal activity which involves the convection and movement of hot waters but is not necessarily connected with an igneous intrusion (see geothermal field; and geothermal gradient).

29) **BOWEN REACTION PRINCIPLE:** A concept, first propounded in 1928 by Norman Bowen, which explains how minerals can respond to the changing equilibrium conditions when a magma is cooled, by either a continuous, diffusion-controlled exchange of elements with the magma or discontinuous melting of the mineral. In a continuous exchange or reaction, solid-solution minerals such as feldspar adjust their composition during cooling by a continuous diffusion of elements between

magma and mineral, whilst in a discontinuous reaction, minerals such as olivine undergo melting at a specific temperature during cooling (the peritectic point) at the same time as a new mineral in equilibrium with the magma begins to crystallize (in this case pyroxene). Bowen suggested a series of these reactions that might take place during the cooling of a tholeiitic basalt magma, the so-called Bowen's reaction series, but pointed out that the series was a simplification of very complex reactions and could be misleading if taken at face value. The specific reaction series for tholeiitic magmas was never intended to become a general reaction series for all magmas.

30) **OROGENY (OROGENESIS):** Mountain building, especially when a belt of the Earth's crust is compressed by lateral forces to form a chain of mountains. There have been many orogenic episodes in the evolution of the crust, each extending over many millions of years. See fold belt; orogeny; orogenic belt; and orogenic cycle.

31) **LINEATIONS:** Are a series of parallel lines on a rock surface, formed by tectonic processes, by the transportation and deposition of sand under upper-flow regime plane-bed conditions, or by the movement of glacial ice over the rock surface.

32) **GROUNDWATER:** All the water contained in the void space within rocks.

33) **SURFACEWATER:** This is any body of water above the ground. This includes streams, rivers, lakes, reservoirs etc.

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION:

This report summarizes a geological mapping exercise initiated by the department of geology and mineral sciences, Kwara state University. The mapping exercise was completed in June 2021 and this report covers the North-Eastern quadrant of Kwara state, Nigeria. The trip covered a period of four days and this was carry-out in Share, Ifelodun Local Government, Kwara State.

The bulk work was done by field mapping of various exposures and outcrops encountered in all locations. Samples were taken from various exposures with the use of hammers and chisel to chip out hand-sized pieces from the whole rock masses. Measurements of numerous intrusions, trends of joint, trends of lineation, veins and some essential structural elements were done with the clinometer compass and distances were calculated with measuring tape, pace lengths and scaling distance from map.

After a period of approximately three days, we were able to give a general description of the lithological distribution of various rock types and delineate structures in the mapped area.

Also traversing was done with the aid of Global Positioning System (GPS) devices and clinometers compasses. The topographical map of the area gave us an insight of regional topography.

1.1 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES:

The main objective of this field mapping is to produce a geological map of the locality showing the rock lithology and the distribution of the rocks.

The objectives of the study includes;

- To enhance students understanding of geological field mapping and the geological history of the area.
- To enhance the ability of students to map a locality individually with the use of certain geologic tools whether or not they are conversant with the area.

- To give a better understanding of the geology of the study area.
- To identify economic importance attached to the mapped area
- Create avenue for students to have dependable experience in geological field mapping.
- Update and produce a geological map of the area

1.2 LOCATION OF THE MAPPED AREA

The mapped portion lies within the latitudes of N 8° 3' 55" and 8° 5' 32.7" and longitudes 5° 08' 39" to 5° 10' 44" E. the area is bordered by lafiagi-share road and Tsaragi.

Fig 1: The map of Share as shown on the google map

1.3 ACCESSIBILITY

Some of the outcrops and exposures are easily accessible because most of them are not too far from each other, while some of them have ridge exposures, road cut, river or stream cut etc. with the aid of the topographical map, the geographical positioning system, we were able to reach several locations and return safely.

Access to the most remote outcrops location was gained by walking and also use of a motorcycles and vehicles were used.

1.4 METHODOLOGY

Firstly, the base map was divided into cells with the aid of the grid system of field mapping.

The method employed in achieving the mapping was with the use of Clinometer compass was to determine the right directions, the base map and GPS were used to locate exposure and other topographic features such as rivers, bridges, and ridges as well as determining the right path to follow. With the aid of the instruments stated above, we were able to confirm the features found on the map and update it with new the features that were observed. We also employed space counting to determine the distance covered on the ground and compare it with that on the map.

The exposure of the rocks in the mapped area were observed for their texture, mineralogy, structure, field relationship and mode of occurrence. The joint system and intrusion was studied for their trend. Samples were collected for laboratory studies. Also with the aid of hand lens, the petrography of the sample was studied.

1.5 INSTRUMENTATION

The mapping was carried out successfully using the essential geological materials as to render effectiveness and accuracy. The materials and functions are tabulated below:

Fig 2: chisel & hammer

Fig 3: Field Boot

Fig 4

Table 1: Functions of the field equipment's used during the mapping exercise

EQUIPMENTS	FUNCTION
Clinometers compass	This was used to determine directions, for taking strike and dip on rocks features like foliation.
Hammer / chisel	These were used to break rocks into respective samples for further analysis.
Geographical positioning system (GPS)	This was used in positioning and also to determine direction and location by recording the present point coordinates.
Mapping board	This was used to hold the map for easy work on the map
Digital camera	This was used to take the picture of features seen on the field. Most especially structural features.
Paper tape	This was used to wrap samples for identification and to tape the map on the board
Measuring tape	This was used to take the width of minor outcrops and also the thickness of intrusions or veins.

Marker/colored pencil	The marker was used to label the samples while the colored pencils were used to represent the rock types seen on the field on its right position on the map with the specific color designated for some rocks e.g. red for granitic rocks. See figure 1.1.
Topographic map of the area	This revealed the geographical and topographical information concerning the mapped area.
Field note	This was used to record information observed on the field with some sketches to complement the recorded information
Hand lens	Due to its magnifying property, it was used to observe mineral compositions and even crystal structures in rock samples for easy viewing and identification.
Field boot and wears	These were worn for protection on the field particular in the bush.
Tracing paper	This is a transparent paper upon which the geologic map is been produced by representation of geological rock units and features found in the process of mapping.
Sample bag	This is a strong, light weighted bag used to convey the samples from the field to the base.

1.6 GEOMORPHOLOGY

Geomorphology refers to the structure, origin, and development of the topographical features of the Earth surface. The geomorphologic features found in the area include mountains, dense and sparse vegetation and farmlands.

1.6.1 RELIEF AND TOPOGRAPHY

The mapped area consists of high and low lands terrain, massive and low lying outcrops. The topography of the area is also composed of minor roads, rivers, with

dense and sparse vegetation (tall trees and grasses). It is dominantly medium to high relief and also presence of low reliefs as well.

1.6.2 CLIMATE

Climate can be defined as a long term prevalent weather conditions of an area, determined by Latitude, position relative to Oceans or continents and altitudes. There are two main climatic conditions in Kwara, namely:

- Rainy Season
- Dry Season

The climatic condition in Share is tropical which is characterised with abundance of tall grasses dotted by few giant trees, except for the river channels which support rain-forest vegetation characterized by deciduous trees.

The rainy season have a good deal of rainfall with average annual rainfall of 1281mm and temperature to be 24.7⁰c while during the dry season, there is little or no rainfall with average annual temperature of 33.44⁰c in a year.

1.7 HUMAN ACTIVITIES

Most of the people of Share practice subsistence farming and petty trading to make their living. The food crops produced abundantly are maize, yam, cassava etc. They also engaged in commercial farming i.e. dealing in cash crop production e.g. cashew nut etc. They also engage in the production of garri from cassava peels.

CHAPTER TWO

FIELD TRIP IN DETAILS

- 2.1 DATE: 22ND June, 2021.
- 2.2 DAY: 1
- 2.3 LOCATION: SHARE (1) (BASIN PLANK)
- 2.4 LONGITUDE: 8.823663°
- 2.5 LATITUDE: 4.948980°
- 2.6 ALTITUDE: 99.0_f

Just around Share junction, an outcrop that is in place is seen. The outcrop is located about 2m from the major road with geometry co-ordinates.

After a close look at the outcrop it is a weathered quartzite that is overlaid by sedimentary rock. This process is known as conformable contact.

The diagram below is a typical example of an Unconformable Contact. Where the crystalline rock is overlaid by younger stratified sedimentary layer. The name of this type of unconformable contact is known as **NON CONFORMITY**.

Fig 5: Non-Conformity

2.7 DATE: 22ND JUNE, 2021.

2.8 DAY: 1

2.9 LOCATION: SHARE (2)

3.0 LONGITUDE: 8.825785°

3.1 LATITUDE: 4.974408°

3.2 ALTITUDE: 1010.8_f

At this location the outcrop here is the same as the previous location 1 but the only difference is that the metamorphic rock of our present location has been buried. At our present outcrop, we were able to identify rocks considering some parameters which are:

- **COLOUR:** rocks are named according to their colour such as brownish, reddish, whitish etc.
- **GRAIN SIZE:** it is easy to identify the size of a grain, Wentworth scale, the origin of sedimentary rock base on Wentworth scale can be sub-divided into:

1. Terigenous/Clastic Origin
2. Chemical/Biochemical Origin e.g. Iron & volcanoclastic origin

The terigenous origin can be divided based on the grain size into:

TERIGENOUS ORIGIN	GRAIN SIZE
CONGLOMERATE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Pebble: 2-64mm• Cobbles: 64-256mm• Boulder: greater than 256mm
SANDSTONE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Very coarse grain sandstone: 1-2mm• Coarse grain sandstone: 0.5-1mm• Medium grain sandstone: 0.25-0.5mm• Fine grain sandstone: 0.125-0.25mm• Very fine grain sandstone: 0.0625-0.125mm

MUDSTONE	Siltstone & Clay stone: anything less than 0.0625mm
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3.3 DATE: 22ND JUNE, 2021

3.4 DAY: 1

3.5 LOCATION: SHARE (3)

3.6 LONGITUDE: 8.806378°

3.7 LATITUDE: 4.962275°

3.8 ALTITUDE: 1045_f

At this outcrop we were thought how to plot a log. To plot a log one should measure from the terrain closer to one i.e. the bottom of the terrain would be zero (0) while the thickness is vertical & the grain size would be horizontal.

Fig 6: the outcrop of the logging.

Fig 7: Log

3.9 Date: 22nd June, 2021.

4.0 Day: 1

4.1 Location: Share (4) (Agbona Ridge)

4.2 Longitude: 8.789278°

4.3 Latitude: 4.964693°

4.4 Altitude: 944.6f

The outcrop at this location, the sedimentary basin is formed as a result of drifting & there are different types of basin, which are:

- Anambra Basin
- Dahomey Basin
- Benue Basin
- Sokoto Basin
- Lokoja Basin

Sandstone consist of Feldspar, Quartz. Feldspar are not stable, they're weak thereby making them to go into solution & it can be weathered into clay by a process called **Hydrolysis**.

There are different types of environment, which are

- Continental Environment
- Transitional Environment &
- Marine Environment

Fig 8: Agbona Ridge.

4.5 Date: 23rd June, 2021.

4.6 Day: 2

4.7 Location: Share (1)

4.8 Longitude: 8.783383°

4.9 Latitude: 4.965020°

5.0 Altitude: 926.8f

At this outcrop we were able to differentiate between a basement complex and the sedimentary basin. The sedimentary basin are places that do not have hard rock, they are comprises of sedimentary rocks at the upper layer and metamorphic rock at the lower layer while the basement complex are the places full of hard rock such as igneous and metamorphic rock. The sedimentary layer of the outcrop has been weathered and washed away, also we realise that lateritization has been done there.

Fig 9

5.1 Date: 23rd June, 2021.

5.2 Day: 2

5.3 Location: Share (2)

5.4 Longitude: 8.288872°

5.5 Latitude: 4.964122°

5.6 Altitude: 974.1

At this outcrop, the basement rock is divided igneous & metamorphic rock, the igneous rock which is formed from molten magma that comprises of 3 materials which are

- Mineral
- Magma fluid &

- Gases

Magma can exist in two ways, which are

- Surface (Extrusive Igneous Rock) or
- Sub-surface (Intrusive Igneous Rock)
- Beneath the earth crust (Plutonic Igneous Rock)

There are different ways in which igneous rock can be differentiated which include;

1. **Texture:** this explain their crystal sizes. Which are: Aphaneritic
Phaneritic

2. **Mineral composition:** this is based on the colouration. Which are;-

- **Felsic:** They are light coloured mineral e.g. Feldspar, Quartz, Silica etc.
- **Intermediate:** They have high light, high dark and other minerals, they are not too dark and not too light.
- **Mafic:** They are made up of magnesium and iron, dark coloured minerals. E.g. Biotite, olivine, pyroxene, iron etc.
- **Ultramafic**

In metamorphic rock the minerals in igneous rock would be separated from each other i.e. separation of dark minerals from light minerals due to the temperature, leading to alignment of minerals in metamorphic rock

5.7 Date: 23rd June, 2021.

5.8 Day: 2

5.9 Location: Share (3)

6.0 Longitude: 8.810410°

6.1 Latitude: 4.968163°

6.2 Altitude: 959.3_f

At this outcrop, the basement complex can be distinguished into 3 major groups, which are;

- **Migmatite Gneiss Complex:** One of the rock that make up **MGC** is the migmatite in the sense that it's as both igneous and metamorphic rock, the rest are Granodiorite, Amphibolite, Gneiss.
- **Schist Belt:** this is a metal sediment, the metal sediment are sedimentary rock that has been metamorphosed/altered as a result of temperature and pressure. There are 2 categories of metal sediments, which include;
 1. **Older Metal Sediment:** this is highly resistant of weathering because it is made up of Quartz, they break along perfect angle.
 2. **Younger Metal Sediment:** they are of low grade and they consist of schist and phyllite. Both shale, granite and gneiss can be metamorphosed to Schist.
- **Older granite/Pan African Granite:** these include;
 1. **Younger Granite:** they are volcanic in nature e.g. Rhyolite, Basalt
 2. **Older Granite:** they include; pegmatite, granite, diorite, granodiorite.

Fig10: Dr. Jimoh, who is about to illustrate how to take a dip & strike.

Fig 11: Strike being taken from a formation to be 118°

Fig 12: Dip being taken from a formation to be 058°E.

6.3 Date: 23rd June, 2021.

6.4 Day: 2

6.5 Location: Share (4)

6.6 Longitude: 8.821193°

6.7 Latitude: 4.951763°

6.8 Altitude: 959.3_f

Below are the readings taken from spring water using a bowl of 13L in volume & a stopwatch. Using the formula:

$$\text{Yield} = \text{volume (L)} / \text{time(S)}$$

Readings:

$$1^{\text{st}} \text{ yield} = 13/13 = 1 \text{ (l/s)}$$

$$2^{\text{nd}} \text{ yield} = 13/14 = 0.92 \text{ (l/s)}$$

$$3^{\text{rd}} \text{ yield} = 13/16 = 0.812 \text{ (l/s)}$$

$$4^{\text{th}} \text{ yield} = 13/21 = 0.626 \text{ (l/s)}$$

$$5^{\text{th}} \text{ yield} = 13/12 = 1.08 \text{ (l/s)}$$

$$6^{\text{th}} \text{ yield} = 13/13 = 1 \text{ (l/s)}$$

$$7^{\text{th}} \text{ yield} = 13/13 = 1 \text{ (l/s)}$$

$$8^{\text{th}} \text{ yield} = 13/13 = 1 \text{ (l/s)}$$

$$9^{\text{th}} \text{ yield} = 13/13 = 1 \text{ (l/s)}$$

$$10^{\text{th}} \text{ yield} = 13/13 = 1 \text{ (l/s)}$$

CHAPTER 3

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION

3.1 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The study area is a typical example of the Precambrian Basement Complex of Nigeria as it is underlain by all the rocks of the Basement Complex. The general trend of foliations is in the N-S to NE-SW or NNE-SSW directions. The metamorphic conditions attained by the rocks in the study are similar to those of rocks in other parts of the Nigerian Basement Complex. The metamorphic imprints in the rocks of the Nigerian schist belts are reflected in their mineralogy and to a lesser extent.

3.2 RECOMMENDATION

With respect to my experience on the field, I will recommend that:

- A local guide is provided to direct students from their base to the nearest outcrop location in that locality in order to ease the mapping exercise and provide time to cover large portions of the designated area with time.

An updated map of the studied area should be provided in order to avoid unnecessary wandering, destabilization of students due to unforeseen changes as some of the features on the map (roads, footpath, rivers etc.) have been replaced by recent ones.

Fig 13: Dr. Jimoh with 200l set (2022/2023)

Fig 14: Dr Adepoju illustrating how sedimentary Basin forms.